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Rheology of a dilute suspension of aggregates in shear-thinning fluids

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Version August 17, 2020 submitted to Micromachines

Abstract: The prediction of the viscosity of suspensions is of fundamental importance in several fields. Most of the available studies have been focused on particles with simple shapes, e.g., spheres or spheroids. In this work, we study the viscosity of a dilute suspension of fractal-shape aggregates suspended in a shear-thinning fluid by direct numerical simulations. The suspending fluid is modeled by the power-law constitutive equation. For each morphology, a map of particle angular velocities is obtained by solving the governing equations for several particle orientations. The map is used to integrate the kinematic equation for the orientation vectors and reconstruct the aggregate orientational dynamics. The intrinsic viscosity is computed by a homogenization procedure along the particle orbits. In agreement with previous results on Newtonian suspensions, the intrinsic viscosity, averaged over different initial orientations and aggregate morphologies characterized by the same fractal parameters, decreases by increasing the fractal dimension, i.e., from rod-like to spherical-like aggregates. Shear-thinning further reduces the intrinsic viscosity showing a linear dependence with the flow index in the investigated range. The intrinsic viscosity can be properly scaled with respect to the number of primary particles and the flow index to obtain a single curve as a function of the fractal dimension.

Keywords: Rheology; shear-thinning fluids; intrinsic viscosity; fractal aggregates; numerical simulations

1. Introduction

Suspensions of solid particles are encountered in a variety of industrial and biological systems. The knowledge of the viscosity and, more in general, of the rheological properties of these materials is fundamental for correctly designing the processing stage and predicting the hydrodynamics resistance. It is well-known that the addition of solid particles in a fluid increases the viscosity as compared with the suspending liquid [1]. Particle shape and size, as well as the solid concentration strongly alter the suspension viscosity giving rise to non-Newtonian phenomena such as shear-thinning and normal stresses [2].

For the simplest case of a dilute suspension of spherical particles in a Newtonian fluid, Einstein calculated that the suspension viscosity is related to the fluid viscosity η_s according to the formula $\eta_s(1 + B\phi)$ where ϕ is the solid volume fraction and the factor B , usually referred as 'intrinsic viscosity', is equal to 2.5 [3,4]. Einstein's calculation was extended by Jeffery to spheroidal particles [5], finding that the intrinsic viscosity depends on the particle orientation and aspect ratio. Specifically, the minimum and maximum average viscosities are obtained for particles aligned along the vorticity axis or tumbling on the flow-gradient plane, respectively. For randomly-oriented particles, integration of

33 the instantaneous intrinsic viscosity for several initial orientations over the corresponding orbits leads
34 to an average value of B higher than the Einstein's coefficient for both prolate and oblate spheroids [6].

35 In many processes, however, the suspended particles have a complex and irregular shape, without
36 symmetry axes or planes. This is, for instance, the case when primary spherical particles undergo an
37 aggregation process and form clusters with fractal-like morphology [7–9]. As for the spheroidal particle
38 case, the prediction of the intrinsic viscosity requires the calculation of the orientational dynamics of
39 the particles subjected to an external shear flow. This approach is carried out in the work by Harshe
40 and Lattuada [10] where the average rigid body resistance matrix of arbitrary shaped clusters made of
41 uniform sized spheres is computed through the Stokesian dynamics method and Brownian dynamic
42 simulations. The intrinsic viscosity was found to be similar to the spherical particle case for clusters
43 with high fractal dimension, indicating no preferential orientation in the flow. Deviations from the
44 Einstein's coefficient was, instead, found for aggregates with low fractal dimension due to their more
45 anisotropic shape.

46 All the aforementioned works deal with Newtonian suspensions. In several applications, however,
47 the suspending fluid shows non-Newtonian properties such as shear-thinning and viscoelasticity.
48 A typical example is in the tire industry where, during the processing stage, particles of carbon
49 black or silica are added to a polymer melt and can agglomerate and form complex structures. It is
50 well-known that non-Newtonian rheological properties alter the suspension rheology as compared to
51 the Newtonian case [11,12]. For instance, for a dilute suspension of spherical particles in a power-law
52 fluid, it has been shown that shear-thinning reduces the intrinsic viscosity [13,14]. Concerning more
53 complex particle shapes, the rheology of a dilute suspension of spheroids in a generalized Newtonian
54 fluid is recently investigated by numerical simulations [15]. Different flows of a Carreau fluid around
55 spheroidal particles are simulated and a homogenization procedure is adopted to obtain the intrinsic
56 viscosity of the suspension as function of the applied rate of deformation, thinning exponent and
57 particle aspect ratio. The results show that the intrinsic viscosity strongly depends on the particle
58 aspect ratio along with the rheological parameters of the constitutive equation [15]. Very recently, these
59 calculations have been extended to a dilute suspension of rigid rods in a power-law fluid showing no
60 similarity of the rheological coefficients between rods and spheroids with large aspect ratio [16]. Similar
61 studies for dilute suspensions of particles with irregular shape, such as fractal-like morphologies, are
62 not available.

63 In this paper, we investigate the rheology of a dilute suspension of aggregates with complex shape
64 suspended in a shear-thinning fluid by direct numerical simulations. Aggregates made of primary
65 spherical particles are built through a fractal-like model. The fluid is modeled by the power-law
66 constitutive equation. The dynamics of a single particle in an unbounded shear flow field is first
67 computed. To this aim, finite element simulations are employed to calculate the angular velocity of the
68 particle for several orientations on the unity sphere. The orientational dynamics is then reconstructed
69 by integrating the kinematic equations for the orientation vector interpolating the angular velocity field.
70 The first-order contribution to the viscosity is computed by means of a homogenization procedure and
71 time-averaged over the particle orbits. The effect of particle morphology and power-law index on the
72 ensemble-average intrinsic viscosity is investigated.

73 2. Mathematical model and numerical method

74 2.1. Governing equations

75 We consider a dilute suspension of rigid, non-Brownian aggregates in a continuous shear flow.
76 The computational domain consists in a single aggregate placed at the center of a spherical domain
77 with radius much larger than the maximum size of the aggregate. A Cartesian reference frame is
78 selected with x , y , and z denoting the flow, gradient, and vorticity directions, respectively. Shear flow
79 boundary conditions are applied on the spherical surface whereas a rigid-body motion is imposed on

Figure 1. Examples of aggregate shapes obtained from the particle-cluster method for $N_p = 20$, $k_f = 1.3$, and $D_f = 1.5$ (a) or $D_f = 2.5$ (c). To avoid numerical issues in the region between tangent particles, the centers of the spheres in contact are connected with a set of cylinders with radius $0.732a$. In panels (b) and (d) the final geometry of the aggregates and the surface mesh are shown.

80 the particle boundary. For the investigated problem (unbounded shear flow) the only relevant particle
 81 kinematic quantity is the angular velocity denoted by $\omega_p = d\theta_p/dt$ with θ_p the rotation angle.

82 The aggregate is made by primary spherical particles with radius a . The morphology is described
 83 by the following fractal equation [17]:

$$N_p = k_f \left(\frac{R_g}{a} \right)^{D_f} \quad (1)$$

84 where N_p is the number of primary particles, R_g is the radius of gyration, D_f is the fractal dimension
 85 (between 1 and 3), and k_f is the fractal pre-factor. Low or high values of the fractal dimension
 86 correspond to more rod-like or spherical-like particles, respectively. Several algorithms have been
 87 proposed to build morphologies obeying the fractal equation [18–21]. In this work, we adopt the
 88 procedure proposed in References [22,23] based on a particle–cluster aggregation method, which
 89 has been verified to generate structures that fulfill the fractal equation also for very few primary
 90 particles [23]. We point out that real fractal aggregates can be approximated by coarsened structures
 91 where each sphere already represents an agglomerate of smaller real primary particles. In Figure 1,
 92 two examples of aggregate morphologies with $N_p = 20$, $k_f = 1.3$, and for $D_f = 1.5$ (Figure 1a) or
 93 $D_f = 2.5$ (Figure 1c) are shown. Notice that the algorithm for aggregate generation is based on a
 94 sequence of pseudo-random numbers. Hence, by changing the random seed, different morphologies
 95 are obtained for the same set of parameters of the fractal equation. Due to the asymmetric shape
 96 of the particle, two orthogonal vectors, p and q , are needed to track its orientation. The selection
 97 of these orientation vectors will be discussed later. Finally, we denote by Ω and $P(t)$ the fluid and
 98 particle domain, respectively. The particle boundary is denoted by $\partial P(t)$ and the surface of the external
 99 spherical domain by Σ .

100 Assuming inertialess conditions and negligible gravity effects, the governing equations for the
 101 fluid domain, $\Omega - P(t)$, read as follows:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0} \quad (3)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = -p\mathbf{I} + 2\eta(\dot{\gamma})\mathbf{D} \quad (4)$$

102 where \mathbf{u} , $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, p , \mathbf{I} , η , and \mathbf{D} are the velocity vector, the stress tensor, the pressure, the 3×3 unity tensor,
103 the viscosity, and the rate-of-deformation tensor $\mathbf{D} = (\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T)/2$, respectively. The viscosity is
104 assumed to be a function of the effective deformation rate defined as $\dot{\gamma} = \sqrt{2\mathbf{D} : \mathbf{D}}$. Equations (2)–(4)
105 are the mass balance (continuity), the momentum balance and the expression for the total stress,
106 respectively.

107 In this work, we consider a power-law constitutive equation for the fluid given by:

$$\eta(\dot{\gamma}) = m\dot{\gamma}^{n-1} \quad (5)$$

108 with m the consistency index and n the flow index. This model predicts shear-thinning for $n < 1$. For
109 $n = 1$, a Newtonian fluid with (constant) viscosity m is recovered.

110 Concerning the boundary conditions, we impose shear flow at the external spherical surface of
111 the domain:

$$\mathbf{u} = (\dot{\gamma}_{\text{ext}}y, 0, 0) \quad \text{on } \Sigma \quad (6)$$

112 with $\dot{\gamma}_{\text{ext}}$ the imposed shear flow. No-slip boundary conditions are set on the particle surface resulting
113 in the rigid-body motion equation:

$$\mathbf{u} = \boldsymbol{\omega}_p \times (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_c) \quad \text{on } \partial P(t) \quad (7)$$

114 where \mathbf{x} is a point of the surface $\partial P(t)$ and \mathbf{x}_c is the particle center of volume. As remarked above, the
115 particle translational velocity is irrelevant for the problem under investigation.

116 To close the set of equations, the hydrodynamic torque acting on the particle needs to be specified.
117 Under the assumptions of inertialess particle and no ‘external’ torques, such balance equation is given
118 by:

$$\mathbf{T} = \int_{\partial P(t)} (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_c) \times (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n}) dS = \mathbf{0} \quad (8)$$

119 where \mathbf{T} is the total torque on the particle boundary $\partial P(t)$ and \mathbf{n} is the unit vector normal to the particle
120 surface pointing from the fluid to the boundary.

121 The solution of the governing equations gives the fluid velocity and pressure fields, and the
122 particle angular velocity. The orientational dynamics can be computed by integrating the following
123 equation:

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\theta}_p}{dt} = \boldsymbol{\omega}_p \quad (9)$$

124 with initial condition $\boldsymbol{\theta}_p|_{t=0} = \boldsymbol{\theta}_{p,0}$.

125 The governing equations can be conveniently made dimensionless by choosing appropriate
126 characteristic quantities for time, length, and stress. As characteristic length, we select the effective
127 radius of the particle defined as the radius of a sphere with equivalent volume V of the aggregate,
128 $R_{\text{eff}} = (\frac{3V}{4\pi})^{1/3}$. The inverse of the external shear rate $1/\dot{\gamma}_{\text{ext}}$ is chosen as characteristic time (giving
129 $R_{\text{eff}}\dot{\gamma}_{\text{ext}}$ as characteristic velocity) and $m\dot{\gamma}_{\text{ext}}^n$ as characteristic stress.

130 With these characteristic quantities, the dimensionless governing equations and boundary
131 conditions read as:

$$\nabla^* \cdot \mathbf{u}^* = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$-\nabla^* p^* + \nabla^* \cdot (2\dot{\gamma}^{*,n-1} \mathbf{D}^*) = \mathbf{0} \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^* = (y^*, 0, 0) \quad \text{on } \Sigma \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^* = \boldsymbol{\omega}_p^* \times (\mathbf{x}^* - \mathbf{x}_c^*) \quad \text{on } \partial P(t) \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{T}^* = \int_{\partial P(t)} (\mathbf{x}^* - \mathbf{x}_c^*) \times (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^* \cdot \mathbf{n}) dS^* = \mathbf{0} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\theta}_p}{dt^*} = \boldsymbol{\omega}_p^* \quad (15)$$

132 where the starred symbols denote dimensionless quantities. Hence, the only dimensionless parameter
 133 appearing in the governing equations is the flow index n . Of course, we need also to consider the
 134 parameters related to the aggregate morphology appearing in Equation (1), that are the number of
 135 particles N_p , the fractal dimension D_f , and the fractal pre-factor k_f . Notice that the radius of the
 136 primary particles a is related to R_{eff} through N_p . Also, the radius of gyration R_g is determined once
 137 the aforementioned three parameters are specified. In what follows, all the symbols (without stars)
 138 will refer to dimensionless quantities.

139 Aim of this work is to predict the viscosity of a dilute suspension of fractal-like aggregates in a
 140 power-law fluid. In the dilute regime, the suspension viscosity can be expressed as:

$$\eta = \eta_s (1 + B \phi) \quad (16)$$

141 where η_s is the matrix viscosity defined by Equation (5), ϕ is the (low) particle volume fraction, and B
 142 is the intrinsic viscosity. Once the local stress field is calculated by solving the governing equations,
 143 the intrinsic viscosity is computed through the numerical homogenization procedure as described in
 144 References [15,24]. In brief, this procedure consists in evaluating first the average power density:

$$\langle P \rangle = \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{D} \rangle = \frac{1}{V_0} \int_{V_f} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{D} dV \quad (17)$$

145 where V_0 and V_f are the suspension and fluid volumes. The suspension viscosity is, then, evaluated as:

$$\eta = \frac{\langle P \rangle}{2\mathbf{D}_{\text{ext}} : \mathbf{D}_{\text{ext}}} = \frac{\langle P \rangle}{\dot{\gamma}_{\text{ext}}^2} \quad (18)$$

146 with \mathbf{D}_{ext} the rate-of-deformation at the external boundaries of the domain that, for a simple shear
 147 flow, reduces to the last term of Equation (18). From the suspension viscosity, we can readily evaluate
 148 the intrinsic viscosity B as:

$$B = \frac{\eta - \eta_s}{\eta_s \phi} \quad (19)$$

149 Due to the anisotropic particle shape, the intrinsic viscosity depends on the particle orientation.
 150 As we will show later, the orientational dynamics is rather complex and neither a steady-state nor a
 151 simple periodic regime is achieved. Hence, we integrate the instantaneous intrinsic viscosity over the
 152 particle orbit for a sufficiently long time T so that the average value defined as:

$$\bar{B} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T B(t) dt \quad (20)$$

153 does not change within a tolerance (chosen as 1%). For each particle morphology, we run several
 154 simulations for different initial orientations. The time-average intrinsic viscosity is, then, averaged
 155 over M initial orientations to get:

$$\langle \bar{B} \rangle = \frac{1}{M} \sum_M \bar{B} \quad (21)$$

156 Finally, to make the results independent of the seed used to generate the aggregates, we
 157 repeat the simulations for different seeds for fixed values of the fractal parameters, and define the
 158 ensemble-average intrinsic viscosity as:

$$\langle \bar{B} \rangle_m = \frac{1}{N_{\text{seed}}} \sum_{N_{\text{seed}}} \langle \bar{B} \rangle \quad (22)$$

159 with N_{seed} the number of seeds.

160 In this work, we fix the fractal pre-factor $k_f = 1.3$, which is a value commonly used in the literature
 161 to describe realistic aggregate morphologies [25]. The suspension intrinsic viscosity is, then, studied by
 162 varying the power-law index, the number of primary particles forming the aggregate, and the fractal
 163 dimension.

164 2.2. Numerical method

165 Except for the simplest case of spherical particles, the intrinsic viscosity is a function of the particle
 166 orientation. Hence, the calculation of \bar{B} in Equation (20) requires the knowledge of the evolution of the
 167 particle orientation dynamics. To this aim, starting from an initial orientation, the governing Equations
 168 (10)-(14) should be solved at each time step followed by the integration of the kinematic Equation
 169 (15). This procedure is time-consuming since, as we will see later, the final integration time must be
 170 3-4 orders of magnitude higher than the characteristic time in order to get an accurate estimate of the
 171 intrinsic viscosity. Furthermore, for each aggregate morphology, the procedure should be repeated
 172 for several initial orientations. However, since no time-derivatives appear in Equations (10)-(14), a
 173 strategy to speed-up the simulations has been recently proposed [26]. We run single-step simulations
 174 for several orientations of the particles (i.e., without performing any time-integration). From these
 175 simulations, we build a look-up table containing the particle angular velocity and the intrinsic viscosity
 176 for each orientation. Then, the orientation dynamics is reconstructed by solving the kinematic Equation
 177 (15) where the angular velocity on the right-hand side is taken by interpolating the simulation data.
 178 Once the look-up table has been constructed, it can be used for calculating the particle orbits for any
 179 initial orientation, thus greatly reducing the computational cost.

180 Let us describe in more details the adopted procedure. Since the particle shape has no symmetry
 181 axes, two (orthogonal) orientation vectors \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{q} are required to identify the orientation of the particle
 182 in a fixed frame. The choice of these two vectors to build the look-up table is done as follows. Let
 183 us consider the unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = (1, 0, 0)$ in the reference frame of the aggregate generated by the
 184 particle-cluster method [22,23]. Notice that this vector identifies an arbitrary direction (depending
 185 on the algorithm used to build the aggregate) and, as such, does not have any physical meaning. A
 186 triangulated icosahedral mesh over the unit sphere is generated, i.e., the unit sphere is divided in
 187 triangles with icosahedral symmetry. The aggregate is then rigidly rotated so that the orientation vector
 188 \mathbf{p} , originally aligned with the unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$, is brought to coincide with the vertices of the triangulated
 189 mesh.

190 For each of these orientations \mathbf{p} , we select the vectors \mathbf{q} as the equally-distributed vectors over
 191 the unit circle around \mathbf{p} . Specifically, the calculation of the vectors \mathbf{q} is carried out by first defining N_q
 192 vectors $\mathbf{q}_{xy,i}$ uniformly distributed over the unit circle in the xy -plane, i.e., $\mathbf{q}_{xy,i} = (\cos \psi, \sin \psi, 0)$ with
 193 $\psi = -\pi + 2\pi(i-1)/N_q$ for $i = 1, \dots, N_q$; then, the vectors \mathbf{q} are computed as $\mathbf{q}_i = \mathbf{R}_{\hat{\mathbf{z}},\mathbf{p}} \cdot \mathbf{q}_{xy,i}$ where
 194 $\mathbf{R}_{\hat{\mathbf{z}},\mathbf{p}}$ is the rotation matrix transforming $\hat{\mathbf{z}} = (0, 0, 1)$ to \mathbf{p} . In this way, the vectors \mathbf{q} are orthogonal to \mathbf{p}
 195 (since \mathbf{q}_{xy} are orthogonal to $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$) and the vector \mathbf{q}_1 corresponds to the transformation of $-\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ according
 196 to the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_{\hat{\mathbf{z}},\mathbf{p}}$. In summary, the aggregate generated by the particle-cluster method is

197 first rotated so that \boldsymbol{p} coincides with one vertex of the icosahedral mesh, and then it is further rotated
 198 around \boldsymbol{p} to get one of the N_q vectors \boldsymbol{q} as discussed above.

199 We select an icosahedral subdivision with triangulation number $T_n = 4$ resulting in 42 vertices
 200 over the unit sphere and $N_q = 12$ for a total of 504 entries (i.e., single-step simulations) in the look-up
 201 table. In this way, the angular distance of \boldsymbol{p} on the unit sphere and of \boldsymbol{q} on the unit circle (around \boldsymbol{p}) is
 202 approximately the same (about $\pi/6$). We have verified that this subdivision is sufficient to assure a
 203 good accuracy of the interpolation.

204 Once the look-up table has been computed, integration of Equation (15) is done by interpolating
 205 the angular velocity. Notice that two kinds of interpolations need to be performed, i.e., one over the
 206 unit sphere (for \boldsymbol{p}) and one over a unit circle orthogonal to \boldsymbol{p} (for \boldsymbol{q}). After obtaining the angular
 207 velocity, we update both orientation vectors instead of the rotation angle θ_p by using quaternions [27].
 208 The entire procedure (interpolation and orientation update) is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Procedure used to update the particle orientation dynamics

```

1:  $\boldsymbol{p}_0, \boldsymbol{q}_0 \leftarrow$  initial orientation
2: for  $t \leftarrow 1, num\_time\_steps$  do
3:   Identify the spherical triangle containing  $\boldsymbol{p}$  with vertices  $\boldsymbol{v}_i$  ( $i = 1, 2, 3$ )
4:   for  $i \leftarrow 1, 3$  do
5:     Compute the rotation matrix  $\boldsymbol{R}_{\boldsymbol{p}, \boldsymbol{v}_i}$  from  $\boldsymbol{p}$  to  $\boldsymbol{v}_i$ 
6:      $\boldsymbol{q}'_i \leftarrow \boldsymbol{R}_{\boldsymbol{p}, \boldsymbol{v}_i} \cdot \boldsymbol{q}$ 
7:     Compute  $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$  and  $B_i$  by interpolating the look-up table with entries  $\boldsymbol{v}_i$  and  $\boldsymbol{q}'_i$ 
8:   end for
9:   Compute  $\boldsymbol{\omega}$  and  $B$  by interpolating  $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$  and  $B_i$  over the spherical triangle in  $\boldsymbol{p}$ 
10:  Update  $\boldsymbol{p}$  and  $\boldsymbol{q}$  using quaternions
11: end for

```

209 The same triangular mesh chosen for building the look-up table is used for interpolation. First
 210 of all, the triangle containing \boldsymbol{p} needs to be identified (step 3 of Algorithm 1). We use the search
 211 procedure described in Reference [28]. The interpolation of the angular velocity and intrinsic viscosity
 212 inside a spherical triangle mesh requires the knowledge of these quantities at the triangle vertices. To
 213 do this, we compute the rotation matrix needed to rotate \boldsymbol{p} on the unit vectors corresponding to the
 214 triangle vertices \boldsymbol{v}_i and apply this rotation matrix to \boldsymbol{q} in order to get the values \boldsymbol{q}'_i in these vertices
 215 (steps 5 and 6). Then, we enter into the look-up table with \boldsymbol{v}_i and \boldsymbol{q}'_i to perform the interpolation (step
 216 7). Notice that the values \boldsymbol{v}_i are already present in the look-up table since, as mentioned above, the
 217 same mesh is used for building the table and for performing the interpolation. This is not the case for
 218 \boldsymbol{q}'_i . Hence, a mono-dimensional interpolation is required over the block of N_q data in the table. This
 219 is done by using a quadratic interpolation. At the end of the inner loop in Algorithm 1 we get the
 220 angular velocity and the intrinsic viscosity in the three vertices of the triangle. A linear interpolation
 221 inside the spherical triangle over \boldsymbol{p} is finally performed to obtain the values of the two quantities in
 222 the desired point [28,29] (step 9). Once the angular velocities are known, the quaternions are updated

Table 1. Mesh and geometrical parameters used in the simulations.

N_p	Δx	R_{ext}	Δx_{ext}	N_{elem}
10	0.20	40	10	~ 20000
20	0.25	40	10	~ 20000
50	0.30	50	20	~ 30000

Figure 2. Probability distribution of the intrinsic viscosity corresponding to the initial aggregate orientations used to build the look-up table, for low (left) and high (right) fractal dimension and three flow indexes. The dashed line represents the median of the distribution.

223 in time by using a third-order Adams-Bashforth scheme. The rotation matrix in terms of quaternions is
 224 constructed and used to update p and q (step 10).

225 The one-step direct numerical simulations are carried out by solving the governing equations by
 226 the finite element method. The particle angular velocity are treated as additional unknowns, and are
 227 included in the weak form of momentum equation. The torque-free condition is imposed through
 228 Lagrange multipliers in each node of the particle surface [30].

229 The spherical primary particles forming the aggregate generated by the particle-cluster method
 230 are tangent. To avoid numerical problems in the region of the contact point, we perform a Boolean
 231 union operation of the spheres with a set of cylinders connecting the centers of the spheres in contact
 232 (that are readily identified since the generation algorithm provides the connectivity list). The radius of
 233 the cylinders is chosen $0.732a$. We have verified that, by reducing the cylinder radius, the rotational
 234 dynamics and the resulting intrinsic viscosity is weakly affected. The aggregate surface is, then,
 235 smoothed and meshed. These operations are performed through the library PyMesh [31]. Examples
 236 of the surface meshes for the aggregates in Figures 1a and 1c are shown in Figures 1b and 1d. The
 237 volume mesh, that is the mesh between the external spherical domain and the aggregate, is made by
 238 tetrahedral elements and is generated by Gmsh [32].

239 Mesh and time convergence, the dimension of the external spherical domain as well as the validity
 240 of the procedure described above are carefully checked. The parameters used in the simulations are
 241 reported in Table 1 where Δx and ΔR_{ext} (made dimensionless by the primary particle radius a) are
 242 the size of the elements on the aggregate surface and the external domain, respectively, R_{ext} is the
 243 radius of the external sphere, and N_{elem} is the number of tetrahedral elements in the volume mesh. We
 244 verified that, by reducing Δx and ΔR_{ext} and increasing R_{ext} by about 20%, the particle angular velocity
 245 and the intrinsic viscosity change by less than 1.5%. The time-step size is fixed at $\Delta t = 0.05$, giving
 246 the same orientation dynamics by repeating the computation with $\Delta t = 0.025$. We have also verified

Figure 3. Box plot of the intrinsic viscosity as a function of aggregate random seed, flow index and fractal dimension. The black dash within each box represents the median of the distribution.

247 the accuracy of the solution of the governing equations for a spherical particle in a power-law fluid
 248 and the validity of the homogenization procedure for the most critical case of $n = 0.4$ by comparing
 249 the results with those reported in Reference [24] (deviations are less than 2%). Finally, the procedure
 250 described in Algorithm 1 is applied to a spheroid. The particle dynamics and the time-dependent
 251 intrinsic viscosity is in excellent agreement with the Jeffery results [6].

252 3. Results

253 In this section we present results by varying the fractal dimension, the flow index, and the number
 254 of primary particles. Specifically, we consider three values for each parameter, i.e., $D_f = [1.5, 2.0, 2.5]$,
 255 $n = [1.0, 0.7, 0.4]$, and $N_p = [10, 20, 50]$. Notice that, since the intrinsic viscosity is normalized with
 256 respect to the aggregate volume, the number of primary particles defines the structure resolution (finer
 257 for many particles) and, for low fractal dimension, it is also connected to the aggregate aspect ratio.

258 Figure 2 shows the probability distribution of the intrinsic viscosity with respect to the same
 259 initial orientations considered to build the look-up table, for the two aggregates reported in Figure 1
 260 and three flow indexes. The dashed lines represent the medians of the distributions, which are all
 261 approximately unimodal. Comparing the results for different fractal dimensions, it can be seen that
 262 at lower D_f the distribution of the intrinsic viscosity is wider, as the particles are more anisotropic
 263 and their orientation becomes more relevant. In particular, B is higher when the aggregate is aligned

Figure 4. Time evolution of the components of the particle smallest principal axis of inertia \mathbf{P} and of the angular velocity around it ω_P , for an initial orientation close to the vorticity axis z . The aggregate is the one reported in Figure 1b, the other parameters are $N_p = 20$, $D_f = 1.5$, and $n = 1.0$.

264 with the gradient direction (i.e., y), and lower when it is aligned with the flow or vorticity direction,
 265 similarly to prolate spheroids. On the other hand, the distribution variance reduces at higher D_f
 266 as the particles are more sphere-like. In agreement with the results for a sphere in power-law fluid
 267 [24], shear-thinning determines a reduction of the intrinsic viscosity, but the shape of the distribution
 268 remains the same.

269 As stated above, to make the results independent of the specific random seed used to generate
 270 the aggregates, for every combination of the other parameters, we repeat the simulations with ten
 271 different seeds. The effect of the specific morphology on the intrinsic viscosity distribution is reported
 272 in Figure 3 with a box plot showing the first, second (i.e., the median), and third quartile of every
 273 distribution. In all cases we find again the same trend seen in Figure 2 with fractal dimension and flow
 274 index, whereas the effect of the random seed is of secondary importance.

275 Since the intrinsic viscosity depends on the particle orientation, which changes with time due to
 276 the imposed shear flow, it is important to reconstruct the particle dynamics. The rotational dynamics
 277 of an irregularly shaped aggregate can be better understood by looking at its principal axes of inertia.
 278 Specifically, let's denote with \mathbf{P} the principal axis corresponding to the smallest moment of inertia,
 279 which for an elongated particle (small D_f) corresponds to its 'natural' orientation. Figures 4 and 5 show
 280 the time evolution of the Cartesian components of \mathbf{P} and the angular velocity around it $\omega_P = \boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \mathbf{P}$,
 281 for the aggregate reported in Figure 1b and two initial orientations. In both cases the orientational
 282 dynamics is rather complex and neither a steady-state nor a simple periodic regime is achieved. Two
 283 periods can be recognized, one shorter connected to the rotation around the vorticity axis z , and
 284 one longer connected to the rotation around \mathbf{P} . When the particle starts with an orientation close to

Figure 5. Time evolution of the components of the particle smallest principal axis of inertia \mathbf{P} and of the angular velocity around it ω_P , for an initial orientation far from the vorticity axis z . The aggregate is the one reported in Figure 1b, the other parameters are $N_p = 20$, $D_f = 1.5$, and $n = 1.0$.

Figure 6. (a) Time evolution of intrinsic viscosity B (blue curve) and time-average intrinsic viscosity \bar{B} (red curve) for the trajectory reported in Figure 4. (b) The same as a for the trajectory in Figure 5.

Figure 7. Probability distribution of the time-average intrinsic viscosity \bar{B} corresponding to the initial aggregate orientations used to build the look-up table and $n = 1.0$, for low (left) and high (right) fractal dimension, parametric in time.

285 the z -axis (see Figure 4), it undertakes a kayaking-like dynamics with approximately elliptical orbits
 286 around the z -axis, more elongated in the x -direction. On the other hand, when the initial orientation
 287 is sufficiently far from the z -axis (see Figure 5), the particle tends to align with the shear plane, i.e.,
 288 P_z progressively reduces, similar to a tumbling motion. At the same time also ω_P decreases, thus
 289 determining an extension of the rotation period around P . The same qualitative behavior of the
 290 aggregate dynamics is observed for shear-thinning fluids.

291 Once the particle orientational dynamics is known, the time evolution of intrinsic viscosity B
 292 and time-average intrinsic viscosity \bar{B} can be reconstructed. Figure 6 shows the trend of B and \bar{B} for
 293 the trajectories seen in previous figures. Specifically, panel 6a refers to Figure 4 (where the particle
 294 undertakes kayaking) and panel 6b refers to Figure 5 (where the particle tumbles close to the shear
 295 plane). In both cases, while B continues to oscillate due to the aforementioned dynamics, after a certain
 296 time, \bar{B} reaches a steady state condition. Notice that such steady state values are different for the two
 297 initial orientations considered. \bar{B} is lower in Figure 6a since the aggregate is mainly aligned with its
 298 longest axis towards the vorticity direction. Conversely, \bar{B} is higher in Figure 6b since, during the
 299 aggregate tumbling motion, P periodically passes close to the gradient direction, which corresponds
 300 to the maximum intrinsic viscosity.

Figure 8. Ensemble-average intrinsic viscosity as a function of fractal dimension, parametric in the number of aggregate primary particles and for different flow indexes (left). Same data as a function of flow index for different fractal dimensions (right). The data standard deviation and trend line are also reported.

301 By repeating this procedure for many orientations, it is possible to obtain the evolution of the
 302 probability distribution of the time-average intrinsic viscosity, as reported in Figure 7 for the usual
 303 two aggregates and $n = 1.0$. Notice that the initial distributions are the same of Figure 2. As just seen
 304 in the previous figure, for low fractal dimension more than one steady state value is present, with
 305 the majority of initial orientations leading to dynamics like the one in Figure 6b with $\bar{B} \approx 11.5$. The
 306 two lower peaks visible for $D_f = 1.5$ at $t = 5000$ correspond to P approximately aligned with the
 307 positive (shown in Figure 4) or negative (not shown) vorticity direction. These last two peaks are close
 308 but not equal since the aggregate has no symmetries. A similar behavior can be observed at high
 309 fractal dimension, but with a longer time needed to reach the steady state. The two peaks visible for
 310 $D_f = 2.5$ at $t = 30000$ are still related to the kayaking and tumbling motion. However, those related to
 311 alignment of P to the vorticity direction or its opposite are not distinguishable because of the more
 312 isotropic particle shape.

313 Finally, averaging on all the initial orientations and random seeds we get the ensemble-average
 314 intrinsic viscosity defined in Equation (22). Figure 8 reports the dependency of $\langle \bar{B} \rangle_m$ on the fractal
 315 dimension and flow index, parametric in the number of primary particles, together with standard
 316 deviation and trend line. In the range considered, $\langle \bar{B} \rangle_m$ decreases with D_f and increases with N_p . The
 317 decreasing trend of $\langle \bar{B} \rangle_m$ with the fractal dimension, previously observed for Newtonian fluids [10], is
 318 related to the aggregate shape and can be justified recalling that the intrinsic viscosity of a suspension
 319 of rod-like particles is higher than the one for a suspension of spheres [6]. For the same reason, the

Figure 9. (a) Ensemble-average intrinsic viscosity normalized with the aggregate hydrodynamic radius as in Equation (23). (b) Same data as panel a normalized by the intrinsic viscosity of a sphere in a power-law fluid. In both panels, the symbols denote the number of primary particles composing the aggregate (lower triangle $N_p = 50$, upper triangle $N_p = 20$, and circle $N_p = 10$) and the colors refer to the flow index (blue $n = 1.0$, red $n = 0.7$, and green $n = 0.4$).

320 number of primary particles forming the aggregate weakly affects the intrinsic viscosity at high fractal
 321 dimension. On the contrary, N_p has a strong influence on $\langle \bar{B} \rangle_m$ for low values of D_f . Indeed, for a
 322 sphere-like aggregate the number of primary particles only defines its resolution, whereas for a rod-like
 323 aggregate it is connected to the aspect ratio that, in turn, determines the viscosity of the suspension [6].
 324 As regarding the effect of the flow index, in agreement with the previous literature for suspensions of
 325 spherical and spheroidal particles [13,15,24], shear-thinning reduces the intrinsic viscosity. Specifically,
 326 as visible on the right column of Figure 8, in the investigated range the intrinsic viscosity linearly
 327 depends on the flow index. As expected standard deviation is lower for high fractal dimensions, since
 328 both initial orientation (see Figure 2) and random seed (see Figure 3) have a relatively minor effect.

329 The intrinsic viscosity shown in the previous figures accounts for the effective volume of the
 330 aggregate that, as discussed in Section 2.1, is computed from the union of spheres and cylinders. An
 331 alternative approach is to normalize the intrinsic viscosity by the aggregate hydrodynamic volume
 332 that, for a set of spherical particles with radius a , is the volume of a sphere with radius $R_H a$, where
 333 R_H is the hydrodynamic radius [10]. The hydrodynamic radius is defined as the radius of a sphere
 334 that gives the same drag force acting on the aggregate in a uniform flow [33], and, in a Newtonian
 335 fluid, it is related to the eigenvalues of the translational mobility tensor. Neglecting the contribution of
 336 the connecting cylinders, the ensemble-average intrinsic viscosity normalized with the hydrodynamic
 337 volume is then:

$$\langle \bar{B} \rangle_{m,H} = \frac{N_p}{R_H^3} \langle \bar{B} \rangle_m \quad (23)$$

338 Figure 9a shows the trend of $\langle \bar{B} \rangle_{m,H}$, in which the values of R_H are taken from the literature
 339 [22,33]. Some remarks are in order: i) Equation (23) and the used hydrodynamic radii assume that
 340 the aggregate is made of tangential spherical particles, ii) the values of R_H are calculated for an

341 aggregate suspended in a Newtonian fluid (notice that the calculation of the hydrodynamic radius
342 for a power-law fluid is not straightforward as, due to the non-linearity of the constitutive equation,
343 the mobility tensor cannot be used for its evaluation). Despite these approximations, the data scale
344 fairly well with respect to the number of primary particles (symbols with the same color in figure).
345 As a consequence of the previous normalization, at high fractal dimension $\langle \bar{B} \rangle_{m,H}$ tends to the value
346 for a spherical particle (i.e., 2.5 in the Newtonian case) [10]. This motivates us to further normalize
347 the data with respect to the intrinsic viscosity of a dilute suspension of spheres in a power-law liquid,
348 given by $B_{\text{sph}} = 0.383 + 2.117n$ [13,24,34]. As visible in Figure 9b, all the data collapse on a single
349 curve. Hence the viscosity of a dilute suspension of aggregates (with the same fractal parameters) in a
350 power-law fluid is completely determined by the fractal dimension. Of course, the prediction of the
351 intrinsic viscosity from the master trend in Figure 9b requires the knowledge of the hydrodynamic
352 radius of the aggregate population.

353 4. Conclusions

354 The viscosity of a dilute suspension of fractal aggregates in a shear-thinning fluid has been
355 investigated. The aggregate morphology is generated through a particle-cluster method combining
356 spherical particles with equal size in order to satisfy the fractal equation. The power-law constitutive
357 equation is used to model the fluid. Finite element simulations are employed to solve the fluid
358 dynamics problem of an aggregate in an unbounded shear flow for a fixed particle orientation.
359 The simulation gives the velocity and pressure fields, and the angular velocity of the aggregate. A
360 homogenization procedure is adopted to obtain the intrinsic viscosity. The simulations are run for
361 a uniform distribution of all the possible orientations, building a database of angular velocities and
362 intrinsic viscosities. The orbits followed by the aggregate are, then, reconstructed by integrating the
363 particle kinematic equation with angular velocity interpolated from the database. Finally, the intrinsic
364 viscosity computed along the orbit is averaged in time and over several initial orientations and seeds
365 used to build the morphology.

366 The rotational dynamics of the aggregate is rather complex, characterized by irregular oscillations
367 and more than one characteristic period. At long times, the aggregate approximately aligns with
368 one of its principal axes of inertia to the vorticity direction, performing a kayaking motion. Hence,
369 multiple regimes depending on the initial particle orientation are possible, thus leading to different
370 time-average intrinsic viscosities. The ensemble-average intrinsic viscosity decreases by increasing the
371 fractal dimension, i.e., from rod-like to sphere-like aggregates. For low values of the fractal dimension,
372 the number of particles forming the aggregate directly affects the aspect ratio and, in turn, leads to
373 relevant variations of the intrinsic viscosity. Shear-thinning reduces the intrinsic viscosity showing a
374 linear dependence with the flow index in the investigated range. Finally, the intrinsic viscosity data,
375 normalized through the hydrodynamic volume and the intrinsic viscosity of a dilute suspension of
376 spheres in a power-law liquid, collapse on a single curve in terms of the fractal dimension.

377 The results presented in this work help to understand the effect of both complex particle shape
378 and non-Newtonian rheology on the intrinsic viscosity of suspensions in the absence of interparticle
379 hydrodynamic interactions. Hence, in some sense, they represent the extension of Einstein result to
380 a (dilute) suspension of fractal aggregates in a power-law fluid. Furthermore, they can be used as
381 starting point to estimate the suspension bulk viscosity at high volume fractions [24,34,35].

382 **Funding:** This work was carried out in the context of the VIMMP project (www.vimmp.eu). The VIMMP project
383 has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant
384 agreement No 760907.

385 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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